

Ikkinchi Jahon Urushidan keyin olib borilgan tadqiqotlar qiyosiy tahlili**Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyazovich****Osiyo xalqaro universiteti Tarix va filologiya kafedrası o'qituvchisi****Sharopov Jahongir Nusratovich****Osiyo xalqaro universiteti tarix yo'nalishi 2-bosqich talabasi**E- mail : sferuz1011@gmail.com

Tel : +998936857755

1950-yillarning o'rtalarida SSSR Fanlar akademiyasi Xorazm ekspeditsiyasi qoraqalpoq etnografik otryadi sovetlar davrida iqtisodiyotdagi sotsialistik o'zgarishlarning qoraqalpoq xalqi hayoti va madaniyatiga ta'sirini o'rgandi.

Yangi etnografik materiallar (kuzatishlar yozuvlari, keksa kolxozchilar, kollektivlashtirish ishtirokchilarining xotiralari eski tuzum parchalanishining chuqurligidan dalolat beradi) T.A.Jdankoga sotsialistik qayta qurishning asosiy bosqichlarini qisqacha, ammo yaxlit ko'rishga imkon berdi. Ilgari qoloq deb kelingan qoraqalpoq xalqining qishloq xo'jaligi, turmushi va madaniyati qanchalar boy ekanini ko'rsatib berdi.¹ U. X. Shalekenov qoraqalpoq dehqonlarining o'tmish va hozirgi hayotini qiyosiy tahlil qildi.²

Shunday qilib, 1938-1959-yillarda Qoraqalpog'iston tarixini arxeologik va etnografik o'rganishning ijobiy natijasi. SSSR Fanlar akademiyasi Xorazm ekspeditsiyasi yordamida avtonom respublikada maxsus arxeologik va etnografik tadqiqotlar rivojlantirildi. Qidiruv marshrutlari avtonom respublikaning butun hududini qamrab oldi, buning natijasida Amudaryoning quyi oqimining batafsil arxeologik va etnografik xaritasi tuzildi.

Qoraqalpog'iston tarixini o'rganishga SSSR FA "Труды Хорезмской археолого-этнографической экспедиции" asarlari muhim hissa qo'shdi. Ular (qoraqalpoq xalqining xo'jaligi, ijtimoiy tuzumi, san'ati tarixini) tavsiflovchi katta hajmdagi materiallar majmuasini to'pladilar, tizimlashtirdilar va ilmiy tahlil qildilar. Mazkur ko'p jildli nashrda yangi arxeologik va etnografik materiallar asosida bir qator muhim Qoraqalpoq xalqining etnik tarixi, etnografiyasi, turmushi va madaniyati muammolari ishlab chiqildi.

Xorazm ekspeditsiyasining ishlari keyinchalik avtonom respublika tarixini yanada kengroq va chuqurroq o'rganish uchun ishonchli asos bo'lib xizmat qildi.

Qoraqalpog'iston iqtisodiyot va madaniyat ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti xodimlari SSSR Fanlar akademiyasi Xorazm arxeologiya-etnografik ekspeditsiyasi ishida faol ishtirok etdilar. Natijada Qoraqalpog'istonda talaba-stajyorlikdan asos solgan olimlargacha yetib borgan yangi yosh olimlar yetishib chiqdi. Keyinchalik mashhur qoraqalpoq olimlari bo'lgan S.Q.Kamolov, U.X.Shalekenov, R.K.Kosbergenovlar bunga misol bo'la oladi.

Umuman olganda, 1938-1959-yillarda Qoraqalpog'istonni arxeologik va etnografik o'rganish katta muvaffaqiyat keltirdi va tarixiy tadqiqotlarni sezilarli darajada kuchaytirdi. Uning natijalari avtonom respublikada tarix fanining yanada rivojlanishiga asos bo'ldi.

40-yillarning oxirlarida olimlar O'zbekiston xalqlari tarixiga oid birinchi yig'ma asar yaratdilar. Unda Qoraqalpog'iston tarixi ham o'z aksini topgan (birinchi jild 1950-yil, ikkinchi jild 1947-

¹ Жданко Т. А. Быт колхозников переселенцев на вновь освоенных землях древнего орошения Каракалпакии. / Труды Хорезмской экспедиции. – М., 1958, – С. 709.

² Шалекенов У. Х. Быт каракалпакского крестьянства Чимбайского района в прошлом и настоящем. / Труды Хорезмской экспедиции. – М., 1958, – С. 269-370.

yil). Bu ish O'zbekiston olimlarining Moskva va Leningrad tarixchilari bilan samarali birodarlik hamjamiyati natijasi bo'lgani e'tiborga molik edi. Bu ajoyib jamoa, yuqorida aytganimizdek, Vatan urushi-yillarida, taniqli olimlarning salmoqli guruhi Toshkentga evakuatsiya qilinganida mustahkamlandi.³

O'zbekiston xalqlari tarixiga oid umumlashtiruvchi asarda qoraqalpoq xalqining o'tmishi ancha keng va har tomonlama aks ettirilgan. Unga "XVI-XVII asrlarda qoraqalpoqlar" maxsus bo'limlari kiritilgan. va "XIII asrda qoraqalpoqlar", shuningdek, "XIX asrning birinchi yarmidagi qoraqalpoqlar" alohida bob.

Ularning barchasi SSSR Fanlar akademiyasining muxbir a'zosi A.A. Semenov tomonidan prof. P.P. Ivanova. "O'zbekiston xalqlari tarixi" sahifalarida Qoraqalpog'iston tarixiga oid ko'plab muhim masalalar, jumladan, qoraqalpoq xalqining etnogenezi, uning siyosiy tarixi, ishlab chiqarish kuchlarining turli bosqichlardagi rivojlanish darajasi va ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzum o'z aksini topgan.

A.A.Semenov qoraqalpoqlar xo'jaligining rivojlanish bosqichlarini va o'zgarishlar dinamikasini aniq kuzatishga muvaffaq bo'ldi; xalq xo'jaligining turli tarmoqlari nisbatida, xususan, qoraqalpoqlarning yarim ko'chmanchi turmush tarzining asosi bo'lgan ko'chmanchi chorvachilik tufayli yerdorlik xo'jaligining rivojlanish jarayoni va uning ulushining bosqichma-bosqich ortib borishini tavsiflab berdi.

Shu asosda A.A.Semenov, umuman olganda, qoraqalpoq jamiyatida qabilaviy tuzum, maorif, feodallar sinfi va ularga qaram bo'lgan dehqonlarning bosqichma-bosqich yemirilishi natijasi bo'lgan ijtimoiy tabaqalanish muammosini to'g'ri qo'ydi.

Shu bilan birga, A.A.Semenovning qoraqalpoqlarning ijtimoiy tuzumi evolyutsiyasiga oid xulosalarida, bizningcha, hamma narsa inkor etib bo'lmas ko'rinmagan. Masalan, uning qoraqalpoq jamiyatida feodal munosabatlarining vujudga kelishi yirik yer egaligining vujudga kelishining oqibati, xolos, degan gapi shunday.

Darhaqiqat, ma'lumki, iqtisodiy negizini ko'chmanchi chorvachilik tashkil etgan jamiyatda feodal munosabatlari tabiiy ravishda vujudga keladi. Tabiiyki, ko'chmanchilar o'rtasidagi feodal tuzum qishloq xo'jaligidagi bir xil turdagi ijtimoiy munosabatlardan farq qiladi. Biroq, bu farqlar pirovard natijada tashqi xususiyatlar bilan bog'liq, lekin ishlab chiqarish munosabatlarining mohiyatiga emas.

"O'zbekiston xalqlari tarixi"da qoraqalpoq-qozoq, qoraqalpoq-buxoro va qoraqalpoq-xivon munosabatlari, ayniqsa, qoraqalpoq xalqining Xiva feodallariga qarshi kurashi ma'lum darajada batafsil aks ettirilgan. Og'zaki xalq og'zaki ijodiga yuksak baho berilgan qoraqalpoq madaniyatining qisqacha tavsifi o'z davri uchun shubhasiz qimmatlidir.

Afsuski, bu umumlashtiruvchi asarda XVII asrning XIX asrning birinchi yarmidagi qoraqalpoq-rus munosabatlari tarixi yetarli darajada yoritilmagan. A.A.Semenov, garchi u bu jarayonning asosiy voqealarini sanab o'tgan bo'lsa-da, uning ocherkida chorizmning qoraqalpoq qabilalariga nisbatan olib borgan siyosatining mohiyatini alohida tahlil qilib ko'rmayapmiz.

Shu bilan birga, u qoraqalpoqlarning Rossiya va O'rta Osiyo xonliklari o'rtasidagi savdo aloqalariga xizmat qiluvchi karvonlarga qilgan hujumlarini baholashda sodda yo'l tutgan. Muallif bu hodisaning sababini faqat qoraqalpoqlar xo'jaligida, sanoatning yo'qligidan birinchi zaruriy tovarlar yetishmasligida ko'rgan. Olimlarning keyingi tadqiqotlari shuni ko'rsatdiki, masalaning

³ История народов Узбекистана. – Т., 1947. – С. 105-106.

bu tomoni chuqur ijtimoiy ildizlarga ega bo'lib, qoraqalpoqlarning xatti-harakatlarini turkman alamani yoki qozoq barimtasiga o'xshash hodisa deb hisoblash kerak.

Umuman olganda, ikki jildlik "O'zbekiston xalqlari tarixi"ning birinchi nashri nashr etilishi respublikamiz tarix fani tarixida muhim voqea bo'ldi. U o'ziga xos kamchilik va kamchiliklarga qaramay, O'zbekiston SSR, xususan, KKASSR tarixiga oid arxeologik, etnografik, yozma va boshqa manbalarni yanada va hatto chuqurroq o'rganish uchun asos va rag'bat bo'ldi.

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